

Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

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ABSTRACT

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This study aims to analyze how the communication message of the sexual violence prevention policy carried out by the Task Force for the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (Satgas PPKS) of Nusa Cendana University is understood by students, and how the message is framed in the context of policy communication. Using the Messaging and Frameworks theory, this study highlights the importance of message framing strategies in shaping audience perceptions, participation, and responses to the issue of sexual violence. The method used is a descriptive quantitative approach by distributing questionnaires to students. The results show that although some students have a good understanding of the objectives of the PPKS policy, there are still information gaps and limitations in communication reach. Communication channels such as social media, seminars, and posters have been used, but have not been fully effective in building active student involvement. The framing of messages that tend to be formal and one-way is one of the causes of the lack of student identification and participation. Therefore, a more participatory, personal, and consistent communication strategy is needed to build collective awareness and create a campus culture that is safe and free from sexual violence.

KEYWORDS:

policy communication, PPKS Task Force, framing, sexual violence, messaging and frameworks

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to explain the policy communication message by focusing on preventing sexual violence by looking at the communication of sexual violence policies in the campus environment which is part of a formal institution. This study raises the communication of sexual violence prevention policies at Nusa Cendana University for the period 2022-2024.

Sexual violence on campus is a serious problem that continues to occur and leaves deep impacts, both psychologically, socially, and academically for victims. In this context, campuses as educational institutions should be safe spaces that guarantee protection for the entire academic community. However, the reality shows that sexual violence still often escapes attention, especially due to low reporting, power relations, and stigma against victims.

Data on sexual violence in Indonesia in 2024 amounted to 13,435 people consisting of 2,900 male victims with a presentation of 19.9% and 11,675 female victims with a percentage of 80.1%. Based on these data, it is known that cases of sexual violence are not an ordinary problem but a problem that must be considered properly.

Many students in higher education experience sexual harassment during their studies at the institution. This then has an impact on the decline in the quality of mental health, physical health and academic results. (Ishak Deding, 2020) Several previous studies have provided evidence that many students who have not completed their studies experience sexual harassment. Victims of sexual violence can receive harassment from various perpetrators, such as friends, staff or teachers from the school. (Bahri & Fajriani, 2015)

Permendikbudristek No. 30 of 2021 became the initial milestone for the presence of formal policies regarding the prevention and handling of sexual violence in higher education. As a follow-up, various universities in Indonesia, including Nusa Cendana University (Undana), formed the Task Force for the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (Satgas PPKS). Since its formation in 2022, the Undana PPKS Task Force has carried out various policy

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Agnes Lidia H.N. et al, Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

communication efforts, such as socialization, seminars, and assistance to victims.

However, the success of policy communication is not only seen from how complete the regulations or work structure of the Task Force are, but also from how students as the main target group interpret the messages and actions taken by the institution. In the context of sexual violence prevention policies, it is important to understand how students respond, interpret, and assess the effectiveness of communication carried out by the PPKS Task Force, including the extent to which they feel involved, protected, and heard.

Understanding the policy communication message from the students' perspective is important because the success of the policy is not only structural but also cultural and participatory. Students' perceptions of sexual violence prevention policies and communications reflect their acceptance or resistance to the program. Therefore, this study focuses on exploring in depth how Nusa Cendana University students interpret the communication message of the sexual violence prevention policy implemented by the PPKS Task Force.

With a qualitative approach, this study will provide an in-depth picture of students' subjective experiences, as well as highlight aspects of policy communication that are considered effective or have not yet touched their needs. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the evaluation and strengthening of policy communication strategies in the campus environment, in order to realize an educational space that is truly safe and free from sexual violence.

The formulation of the problem in this study is: how is the communication message of the sexual violence prevention policy carried out by the PPKS Task Force for students of Nusa Cendana University? With the aim of analyzing the meaning of the communication of the sexual violence prevention policy carried out by the PPKS Task Force from the perspective of students of Nusa Cendana University.

Literature review

There are four journals reviewed, namely journals by Deding Ishak (2020), Rifki Elindawati (2021), Sophia Sukma Fatimah Yasmin & Rhafidilla Vebrynda (2024), and the Undana Nggili Agnes student perspective journal (2025). These four studies have a common thread in discussing sexual violence on campus, but with different highlights, approaches, and theoretical focuses. Deding Ishak's journal (2020) focuses on demographic and structural factors that increase the risk of sexual harassment in educational institutions. His research found that women, gender and sexual minorities, and traditional students are at higher risk of becoming victims of sexual harassment, especially as they spend more time at the institution. Although it does not discuss policy communication directly, this journal

emphasizes the need for identity-based policies and risk data to create a safe academic environment.

Meanwhile, Rifki Elindawati's journal (2021) uses a Foucaultian feminist perspective to explore sexual violence as a result of unequal power relations, patriarchal culture, and the social construction of victim-blaming. This journal found that women are the main targets of sexual violence because of their subordinate position in the campus social system. The power relations between lecturers and students or between seniors and juniors in campus organizations are fertile ground for violence, which is exacerbated by the fear of victims to report. This finding is in line with your research in terms of the importance of students' understanding of their position in the campus system, although Rifki's journal focuses more on power analysis than communication strategies.

Meanwhile, the journal of Sophia Sukma and Rhafidilla Vebrynda (2024) highlights students' perceptions of the importance of safe spaces from sexual violence on campus, with a quantitative approach that focuses on students' awareness, participation, and attitudes in creating a campus environment free of violence. The results show that although the majority of students are aware of the importance of safe spaces, many still do not understand the reporting mechanism and do not feel actively involved in prevention efforts. A clear similarity with your research is that both discuss student perceptions, but the difference lies in the focus: your research assesses how the PPKS Task Force's policy messages are understood and received, while this journal assesses general attitudes towards the issue of safe spaces.

Finally, the author's own research conducted at Nusa Cendana University focuses on how students interpret and respond to communication messages on sexual violence prevention policies by the PPKS Task Force. With a qualitative approach and the theory of Messaging and Frameworks, you found that many students did not fully understand the policy, the messages delivered were one-way and less personal, and communication channels such as social media and seminars had not been optimally utilized. This finding provides different added value compared to the other three journals because it directly evaluates the effectiveness of institutional communication strategies and the perceptions of recipients, not just risk structures or power relations.

Overall, these four journals highlight the urgency of addressing sexual violence in higher education, from various perspectives: structural-demographic (Deding Ishak, 2020), power relations and gender (Rifki Elindawati, 2021), student collective consciousness (Sophia & Rhafidilla, 2024), and policy communication strategies (Nggili Agnes 2024). What they have in common is that they all acknowledge the importance of campus institutional intervention and protection for victims, but the differences reflect a spectrum of approaches: from sociological, feminist, participatory, to communicative. Your research complements the literature by

Agnes Lidia H.N. et al, Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

presenting a highly contextual portrait of student perceptions, especially in seeing how policy messages are truly interpreted by their main targets.

METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study is a qualitative method. Because the purpose of qualitative research is to understand certain social situations, events, roles, groups, or interactions (Creswell, 2014). descriptive study type. This approach was chosen to describe and understand in depth how Nusa Cendana University students interpret the messages of sexual violence prevention policies conveyed by the PPKS Task Force. The main focus is on their meaning, perception, and interpretation of policy messages, within the framework of the Messaging and Frameworks theory.

The data in this study were collected using an open-ended interview technique based on a questionnaire, which was distributed to informants in the form of an online form. This interview aims to explore students' understanding, perceptions, and interpretations of policy communication carried out by the PPKS Task Force of Nusa Cendana University. In addition, researchers also conducted a documentation study to see the contents of the policy, socialization materials, and other relevant public information.

The main instrument in this study was an open-ended questionnaire designed based on the Messaging and Frameworks theory. The questions in the questionnaire directed respondents to describe their understanding of the content of the policy, how it was delivered, messages that were considered strong or weak, and the meanings they captured. This instrument allowed informants to answer with an open narrative that described personal and contextual perspectives.

The subjects in this study were active students of Nusa Cendana University who had participated or at least knew about the socialization of the PPKS policy by the campus Task Force. The number of informants was 6 people, selected using purposive sampling techniques. The criteria for selecting informants were:

1. Active student of Nusa Cendana University.
2. Knowing or having participated in the PPKS Task Force socialization.
3. Willing to provide opinions honestly and openly.
4. Coming from a variety of study program backgrounds and educational levels.

Data analysis is the process of systematically searching and compiling transcripts, journal notes, and other materials that researchers collect to enable researchers to find findings. In addition, data analysis is an effort or step to explain the data obtained in narrative, descriptive or tabular form. The conclusion of the data analysis carried out has led to an exploratory conclusion.(Fiantika R. Feny, 2022)

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis. The steps include:

1. **Data reduction**– filter the informant's answers to find the essence of each statement.
2. **Categorization**– grouping data into themes based on concepts in the Messaging and Frameworks theory (e.g.: message content, delivery method, emotions, identity, and values).
3. **Interpretation** – analyze the relationship between themes, the meaning of the messages captured, and the effectiveness of policy communication according to student perceptions.
4. **Drawing conclusions**– compile a final narrative based on the patterns found from the informant's answers.

To ensure the validity of the data, this study uses source triangulation and member check. Triangulation is done by comparing the results of interviews from several informants who have different backgrounds. Meanwhile, member checks are done by asking for confirmation from informants regarding the summary of the interview results to ensure that the researcher's interpretation is in accordance with the intent of their answers. In addition, an audit trail is done by documenting the data collection process systematically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results :

From the results of the research that the researcher conductedn, researchers put forward several important points related to policy communication messages, namely:

Understanding the PPKS Policy Message

The study shows that Nusa Cendana University students' understanding of the message of the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) policy still varies. Some students showed a fairly good understanding of the content and objectives of this policy, especially regarding prevention efforts, protection of victims, and action against perpetrators. One student stated, "As far as I know, the policy helps prevent and overcome or handle cases that are now increasingly occurring on campus, especially among students."

However, there are also students who are not aware of the existence of the policy or the task force that implements it. One respondent answered briefly, "No," when asked if he knew about the PPKS policy on campus. Even when asked about the existence of the PPKS Task Force, there were students who answered, "Just found out about it." This shows a significant information gap among students.

Regarding information sources, the majority of students learned about the PPKS policy through social media, posters, and campus socialization activities. One student said, "I learned about it from posters/banners displayed on campus." While another student added that information was

Agnes Lidia H.N. et al, Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

conveyed, "Through socialization on campus, either through seminars or at the initial student orientation or PKKMB."

Although communication channels have been used, not all students can grasp or remember the core message of this policy. Some admitted that they had never seen or heard the information directly. This indicates that the communication strategy used by the PPKS Task Force needs to be strengthened, especially in terms of continuity of delivery, audience-based approaches, and framing messages that are more persuasive and relevant to students' experiences. A complete understanding of the policy message is essential to building collective awareness in creating a safe campus environment free from sexual violence.

Message Framing

In general, the framing of messages carried out by the PPKS Task Force was considered quite good by some students, because they considered the messages delivered to be short, concise, and emphasized prevention, handling, and protection against sexual violence. The goal is clear: to create a campus environment that is safe, comfortable, and free from sexual violence. Students who had received the messages stated that the messages from the Task Force were sufficient to build their understanding of various forms of sexual violence, including those they had not previously known about. This gave rise to empathy, awareness, and responsibility to participate in preventing and handling sexual violence. One student said, "These messages foster empathy and social responsibility, as well as the awareness that being silent or allowing it means supporting the occurrence of violence."

However, not all students feel the same way. Some stated that they had never heard or seen the message from the PPKS Task Force directly, indicating a gap in the dissemination of information. In addition, some students considered that although the message was delivered well, its implementation was not consistent in the field. One respondent said, "Yes and no, yes because the message delivered is in accordance with the consequences. No because there is no direct action in the field related to preventing sexual violence." This shows that a well-framed message still needs reinforcement through real action so that it is truly believed and accepted by students.

There is also criticism regarding the lack of effective use of media in conveying messages. Students hope that the framing of messages is carried out with a more humanistic approach, does not judge victims, and is repeated so that it sticks as a campus culture. One student stated, "The message from PPKS must also be victim-oriented so that victims feel safe and not pressured." Therefore, in the future, the PPKS Task Force needs to review their framing strategy by ensuring that the message is not only strong in content, but also reaches a wider audience and is delivered through appropriate and consistent channels.

Communication Channels and Response

In general, students considered social media to be the most effective communication channel in conveying PPKS policy messages because it can reach more students quickly, cost-effectively, and in accordance with the habits of the current generation who are very active on digital platforms. However, they also acknowledged that the PPKS Task Force's social media had not been optimized optimally and was still passive. Several students also mentioned that posters on campus and seminars still had an influence, especially when combined with digital media. One student said, "I think all media can have a positive effect, but for today's era, social media is more suitable." This opinion reinforces the view that a combination of communication strategies is needed, with the main focus on the platforms that are most relevant to students.

Regarding the response to the messages delivered, some students felt that they were being paid enough attention, but their involvement in efforts to prevent sexual violence was not yet optimal. They wanted a communication approach that was not only informative, but also invited active participation. For example, students mentioned the need for direct invitations or interactive activities so that they felt they were truly part of the prevention movement. One student said, "I feel that the channels used are quite effective if the messages are delivered through media that students often access... but my involvement is still limited because there have been no direct invitations or interactive activities."

This response shows that policy communication must be accompanied by participatory strategies so that students are not only recipients of messages, but also active actors in the implementation of sexual violence prevention. In addition, there is a collective awareness that the success of the policy is very dependent on the involvement of all parties in the campus environment. One student emphasized, "I feel that if we are not involved or allow sexual violence on campus in any form, it is the same as supporting the occurrence of the violence." This view shows that the effectiveness of communication is not only measured by how often the message is delivered, but also by how far the message is able to arouse empathy and drive real action from the academic community.

Hope and Response

In general, students showed great expectations for the performance and communication of the PPKS Task Force in the future, especially in introducing policies more actively and comprehensively. Many students felt that the existence of the PPKS Task Force was not yet widely known, so they hoped for increased socialization and education that was not only formal, but also able to touch the emotional side and personal involvement of students. One student said, "I hope that in the future the PPKS Task Force can carry out comprehensive, sustainable, and easily accessible education... with an interactive and consistent approach."

Agnes Lidia H.N. et al, Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

This illustrates that students want closer communication, not just informative but also inviting participation.

On the other hand, students also expressed that the Task Force's communication approach so far has tended to be rigid and one-way. They felt that there needed to be a change in the way messages were conveyed to be more down-to-earth, such as through real stories or campaigns that are relevant to students' lives. One response that reflected this was, "Many of the messages conveyed felt formal and rigid... I think the approach needs to be more personal—for example by presenting real stories, testimonials, or relatable campaigns."

Regarding participation, some students felt that the PPKS policy actually opened up opportunities for active involvement, but that space had not been maximized. They wanted clarity in the participation mechanism, as well as more transparent communication about how they could contribute. One student said, "Students need to know that they are needed, not just as spectators, but as part of the solution." This shows a desire to be involved, as long as the information and invitation are conveyed clearly and consistently.

Overall, students' expectations and responses to the PPKS Task Force are very focused on strengthening effective, interactive, and empowering communication. They not only want to be informed, but also invited to play an active role in creating a campus environment that is safe from sexual violence.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that policy communication on the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) at Nusa Cendana University still faces various challenges in terms of audience understanding, message framing, effectiveness of communication channels, and active involvement of academics. To analyze this phenomenon in more depth, the discussion will use the Messaging and Frameworks theory approach, which emphasizes that effective policy messages must consider what to say, how to say it, through which channels, and why it matters (Nisbet, 2009).

1. Understanding Policy Messages: Information Inequality and Audience Inaccessibility

Variations in students' understanding of the PPKS policy indicate that the communication process has not succeeded in reaching all target groups evenly. In the Messaging and Frameworks framework, the importance of understanding the values, experiences, and backgrounds of the audience is key to messages being received and internalized (Lakoff, 2004). The ignorance of some students even about the existence of the PPKS Task Force indicates a gap between the content of the message and the reach of the audience, which

indicates the need for audience segmentation and a context-based approach.

This finding is in line with the research of Sophia Sukma Fatimah Yasmin & Rhafidilla Vebrynda (2021) which states that although students support campus safe spaces, many of them are not aware of reporting procedures or the existence of supporting institutions. This confirms that the information gap is an unresolved structural problem of campus communication.

According to the Audience-Centered Messaging theory (Kahan, 2010), the success of policy communication depends on the sender's ability to speak within a value framework that is understood by the audience. If basic values such as safety, justice, or empathy are not used as entry points, then the policy will be considered far from the reality of students. Deding Ishak's journal (2020) also highlights that female students and minority groups are more vulnerable to harassment due to social structures and lack of institutional understanding of their identities, which further widens the gap between policies and the perceptions of target audiences.

2. Message Framing: Building Awareness, But Lacking Consistency

The framing of the message by the PPKS Task Force, which emphasizes prevention, victim protection, and campus comfort, has succeeded in reaching some students. Framing that targets empathy and social responsibility is in accordance with the moral-based messaging approach (Lakoff, 2004), namely conveying policy issues in a moral frame that can arouse emotions and a sense of responsibility. The awareness that allowing sexual violence to occur is the same as supporting it shows success in triggering a moral response from some audiences.

However, Messaging and Frameworks emphasizes that framing must be accompanied by consistency and reinforcement at the implementation level (Nisbet, 2009). When students judge that real actions are not in line with the content of the message, the credibility of the communication is weakened. Rifki Elindawati's (2021) research strengthens this finding, that one of the causes of victims' distrust of the system is because power relations have never been clearly challenged by the institution. In some cases, communication that is not accompanied by concrete action is considered merely a formality. This means that a good message will lose its impetus if it is not supported by actions that can be observed in the field.

3. Communication Channels and Response: Suboptimal Social Media and Low Interactivity

In the theory of Messaging and Frameworks, the selection of communication channels is an important component to ensure the effectiveness of message delivery. Younger generations such as students are more responsive to social media that is fast, concise, and visual (Rainie & Wellman, 2012). However, even though social media has been used, students consider its use by the Task Force to be passive and not sufficiently attention-grabbing. This indicates that channel adaptation has not been fully implemented.

Research by Sophia Sukma (2024) shows that students receive more information from social media, but there is still minimal interaction and response from the campus. Meanwhile, in the Deding Ishak journal (2020), it was stated that one-way communication from institutions ignores the active involvement of students as recipients of policies.

According to the principle of Participatory Communication (Servaes, 2008), the audience is not enough to just receive messages, but needs to be involved as subjects who actively contribute. This was also stated in Elindawati's research (2021), where the dominance of patriarchy in the campus structure makes policies tend to be made top-down and do not touch on the daily aspects of students. Therefore, the success of communication channels is highly dependent on interactivity and emotional involvement.

4. Expectations and Responses: The Need for Personal, Emotional, and Empowering Communication.

Students hope that the PPKS message will not only be delivered formally, but also through a personal and down-to-earth approach. This is in line with the principle of value-based messaging, which prioritizes narratives and real experiences as the main medium for building emotional closeness with the audience (Kahan, 2010). The desire to see victim testimonies, real stories, and relatable campaigns shows the importance of narrative in shaping collective consciousness.

In Rifki Elindawati's research, the importance of human-centered storytelling is highly emphasized. Real stories from victims, as well as narratives that emphasize power inequality and stigma, are considered more powerful in raising awareness than normative slogans. In addition, Deding Ishak (2020) also showed that student victims of sexual violence often do not report due to a lack of psychological safety, which should be

overcome with empowering and empathetic communication.

In general, these findings support the view that effective policy communication must be based on the integration of message content, delivery methods, audience values, and their active participation in the change process. By implementing the Messaging and Frameworks framework, the PPKS Task Force can strengthen its communication strategy to be more adaptive, touch the emotional side, and encourage the involvement of academics in creating a campus environment that is safe from sexual violence. The four comparative journals support this conclusion through complementary perspectives: from student awareness and participation (Sophia et al.), the importance of identity-based and experience-based communication (Deding Ishak), to understanding power relations and the need for transformative communication (Rifki Elindawati).

CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze how Nusa Cendana University students interpret the communication message of sexual violence prevention policies delivered by the PPKS Task Force. Based on the results of the research and analysis, it can be concluded that the policy communication carried out by the PPKS Task Force still faces various obstacles both in terms of understanding, message framing, selection of communication channels, and audience involvement.

First, there is a gap in understanding among students regarding the content and objectives of the PPKS policy. This shows that the policy message has not succeeded in reaching the audience evenly and deeply. Second, although the framing of the message has emphasized moral values such as empathy, protection, and prevention, students feel that the message conveyed is not consistent with real actions in the field, thus reducing its effectiveness. Third, the communication channels used, such as social media, posters, and seminars, are not fully optimal and are one-way. The lack of interactivity causes students to be less actively involved in efforts to prevent sexual violence. Fourth, students hope for a more personal, emotional, and empowering communication approach, so that they feel truly involved in creating a safe campus culture.

Overall, the success of sexual violence prevention policy communication is highly dependent on the Task Force's ability to convey

Agnes Lidia H.N. et al, Student Perspectives in Understanding Sexual Violence Prevention Policy Messages: A Case Study at Nusa Cendana University

messages that are relevant to the audience's values and experiences, as well as encouraging the active participation of academics in the process of social change.

SUGGESTION

1. Improve Audience Segmentation Strategy

The PPKS Task Force needs to conduct more specific audience mapping and develop communication strategies that are tailored to the characteristics of students from various backgrounds. A context-based approach and local needs will increase the relevance of the message and the effectiveness of its reception.

2. Strengthening Framing and Consistency of Implementation

The framing of the message needs to emphasize empathy, justice, and courage to report, but must be accompanied by concrete actions in the field so that the message does not lose credibility. Consistency between message and action is very important in building student trust in campus institutions.

3. Optimization of Interactive Communication Channels

Social media as the main channel needs to be managed actively and creatively, for example through visual campaigns, victim narrative-based content (testimonials), and live Q&A sessions. The combination of digital and face-to-face media must function as a dialogue space, not just a one-way delivery of information.

4. Development of Empowering Communication

The Task Force's communication should not only be informative but also transformative—that is, touching on emotional aspects, providing a sense of security, and opening up space for active participation for students. Personal and humanistic narratives are more effective in building collective awareness.

5. Periodic Evaluation and Student Involvement

The Task Force is advised to conduct regular evaluations of the effectiveness of communication strategies through surveys or discussion forums, as well as to involve students in the design and implementation of socialization programs so that policies do not feel exclusive from top to bottom.

By implementing a more adaptive, participatory, and empathetic communication approach, it is hoped that the Nusa Cendana University PPKS Task Force can build a policy communication ecosystem that encourages the courage to report, academic solidarity, and the creation of a campus environment free from sexual violence.

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